

Special Relativity, Action-Reaction and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

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In (1), we suggested that the special relativistic Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ pointed towards the notion of invariance not simply across frames with different constant velocities, $-v$, but over all free particles. We thus suggested using $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ to demonstrate such an invariance, noting that $-Et$ and px terms are independent (just as $(px)x$, $(py)y$ and $(pz)z$ terms are for a full $p \cdot r$).

In this note, we wish to investigate the suggestion of (1) in more detail. First, we note that for a given frame with $-v$, E and p are related by $Ev = p$ ($c=1$) (for a particle with rest mass) and so it is difficult to see independence between the two even though they represent different components of a 4-vector. Similarly $x' = vt'$ for a particle with rest mass and one again does not have independence in trajectory even though one has the 4-vector (x, ct) .

In order to see independence between E and p , we suggest that one must consider at least two particles with different rest masses, different E values, but the same p , hence yielding the same impulse hit. This, however, suggests two different moving frames, each with a different $-v$ and not one. We ask: How does one introduce two frames in a natural manner? We suggest that if one considers two different rest masses m_{o1} and m_{o2} at rest, one has a total p of 0, each particle has equal and opposite momentum, but different energies and there is one frame. Using the notion of action-reaction, one may suggest that if m_{o1} and m_{o2} are joined by a spring which is released, they may achieve equal and opposite momenta (linked to two different frames with $-v_1$, $-v_2$) and have different energies. The two have equal momenta, but different E values which, we argue, suggests independence of p and E . This may be verified by noting that the two are associated with independent measurements (impulse hits on a target versus distance traveled in a repulsive potential, as discussed in (1)).

Similarly, one may have the same E for two particles, but different momenta. In such a case, a different kind of measurement (distance traveled in a repulsive field) does not distinguish between the E values. We note that the action-reaction approach is directly connected with the concept of conservation of momentum. We argue that this reasoning suggests that E and p are independent even though $Ev = p$ ($c=1$) for a particle with rest mass might suggest otherwise. As a result, $-Edt + p dx$, should have $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ in order to demonstrate such independence. Otherwise, there is a correlation between the two terms and they are not independent.

As a result, we argue that $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$, i.e. free particle quantum mechanical properties, are not only linked with the special relativistic Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$, but also with the notion of conservation of momentum and action-reaction. Even though one may use $-Et + px$ for a single particle, the independence of E and p is really seen through considering at least two particles at rest with different masses which break apart with equal and opposite momenta.

Special Relativity and Independence of E, p and x, ct

Special relativity uses 4-vectors such as: $(c \text{ p vector}, E)$ and (r, ct) . From 3-space, it is known that p vector components and r vector components are independent, but the idea of special

relativity is to create a 4-space with four independent components. The problem is that if one considers a particle with rest mass m_0 at rest and transforms it (using a frame moving with $-v$ in the x direction), then

$$E = p \quad (c=1) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad x' = vt' \quad ((1b))$$

((1a)) and ((1b)) do not suggest independence of E and p and x' and t' . Rather, p (all in the x direction) is a scaled value of E and x' a scaled value of t' . As a result, it is somewhat difficult to directly see the suggestion of (1), namely that one have invariance for the terms of the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z \quad ((2))$$

for all free particles. In one dimension, ((2)) becomes $-Et+px$ and $E=p$ suggesting E and p are not independent, with a similar property holding for x' and t' . This invariance in (1) implies that:

$$dt = \hbar/E, \quad dx = \hbar/(px), \quad dy = \hbar/(py) \quad \text{and} \quad dz = \hbar/(pz) \quad ((3))$$

Furthermore, ((3)) ultimately leads to the free particle wavefunction: $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$ ((4)), which allows for conservation of energy if one integrates $\exp(iE_1 t) \exp(-iE_2 t)$ over t or conservation of momentum if one integrates $\exp(-ip_1 \cdot r) \exp(ip_2 \cdot r)$ over dr . It is not clear how conservation of energy or momentum results from the treatment of a single particle Lorentz invariant ((3)). We thus try to examine the ideas of (1) in more detail.

The Notion of Action-Reaction

Given that $p=vE$ ($c=1$) and $x'=vt'$ for a particle with rest mass, and that $dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ leads to conservation of energy and momentum through $\exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r)$, we try to find independence of p and E by considering two particles with different rest masses. We have already suggested in previous notes that p may have the same value for products of different masses and speeds. In other words, one needs m_01 and m_02 and two different frames, $-v_1$ and $-v_2$.

We suggest that one may consider a single frame with rest mass m_01 connected to m_02 by a compressed spring. In such a case, the particle energies are different, total momentum is 0 and each particle has 0 momentum (i.e. equal and opposite momentum). If the spring is released and one insists on the Newtonian action-reaction principle, one might argue that the two masses attain the same momentum although having different energies and velocities. In such a case, one sees the same p magnitude value mapped to two different energy values suggesting that one should consider E and p as independent if there exists a physical way of measuring these statements. In fact, p is proportional to impulse and so the two particles with different energies strike a target in the same way (same impulse). In a repulsive field, however, different energies E mean that each particle travels a different distance. A similar argument may be made for having the same E for two particles and different p values. Thus, the notion of independence of

E and p only appears if one considers at least two particles and uses the idea of action-reaction to establish conservation of momentum. We suggest that it is the two ideas:

- (A) p and E being independent in terms of measurement
- (B) Conservation of p and E

ultimately allow one to consider the Lorentz invariant for a single free particle ((3)) and argue that the various terms should be independent. To be independent, $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$, as different weights would suggest a relationship between the various terms. Here $c=1$. Given that conservation of E and p are part of the initial assumptions required to develop the results: $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$, one would expect that conservation of momentum should manifest itself in any final results.

Conservation of Momentum and Energy

In the above section, we argue that the free particle quantum mechanical results, $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$, follow not only from the independence of p and E, but from conservation of momentum and energy (i.e. action-reaction). We suggested that one requires at least two particles to demonstrate that p and E can be independent in terms of measurement, (because otherwise $E = pc$ (for a particle with rest mass)). This demonstration of E-p independence is linked with conservation of momentum.

The results $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$ may be shown to be consistent with a complex probability:

$$\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) ensures that gradations appear in t, x, y and z, but that one has equal probability within each gradation. Furthermore, $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$ complex conjugate $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r) = 1$ showing equal probability in all t and r, i.e. erasing the gradations. Conservation of momentum and energy are, however, also associated with ((4)) because:

$$\int dt \exp(i E_1 t) \exp(-i E_2 t) = 0 \text{ if } E_1 \neq E_2 \quad ((5a)) \text{ and}$$

$$\int dx dy dz \exp(-i p_1 \cdot r) \exp(i p_2 \cdot r) = 0 \text{ if } p_1 \text{ vector } \neq p_2 \text{ vector} \quad ((5b))$$

Conservation of energy and momentum are used to establish $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$, but then explicitly manifest themselves in ((4)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) we suggested introducing $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$ by making all terms in: $A = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z$ equivalent, i.e. equal to 1. If different terms had different values, they would not be independent, we argue. This suggests an invariance across all free particles.

We point out that given a rest mass m_0 , $E = pc$ ($c=1$) and $x' = vt'$ as seen in a frame moving with $-v$. As a result, even though special relativity uses 4-vectors which treat t as a fourth independent dimension apart from the r vector and E as a fourth independent dimension, apart from p vector, in one dimension $E = pc$ and $x' = vt'$ do not seem to show this independence. We suggest that to see a physical independence between E and p , one requires at least two particles.

In one particular scenario, one has m_{01} and m_{02} at rest with a compressed spring in between. The rest masses (energy) of the two particles differ, but total momentum is 0 as is the momentum of each particle. If the spring is released and one insists on the action-reaction principle, one might suggest that one particle receives a final p and the other, $-p$. Once again p total is 0, one has p and $-p$ and different energies. As a result, particles with the same p can have different E . The question then becomes: Are there physical implications? There are, because p is proportional to impulse against a target. Thus, m_{01} and m_{02} yield the same impulse measurement, but travel different distances in a repulsive field. A similar argument holds for the same E and different p values. This, we argue, establishes the physical independence of E and p and allows one to consider $-Edt + p dx$ as leading to $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$. We note that conservation of momentum (action-reaction) has been used in establishing the independence and so this quantum result does not simply follow from the Lorentz invariant. As a result, conservation of momentum is inherent a priori in the derivation. As a result, this conservational property should manifest itself later. If one creates $\exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r)$, one sees that it inherently contains conservation of both energy and momentum through ((5a)) and ((5b))

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Static versus Dynamic Variables, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2024)